

TRE Survey by EOSC-ENTRUST 2025

Introduction to the survey

Thank you in advance for taking the time to respond to this survey by the EOSC-ENTRUST project's work on trusted research environment (referred to as TRE or 'environment' from here on) providers. This survey is based on a survey done previously by HDRUK*, as well as the 2024 survey** by the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

Please read the questions carefully before answering. If you want to browse the questions before submitting responses, you can find a PDF version of the survey here:

This survey takes approximately 20 minutes to complete in one sitting.

If a question is not applicable to the environment in question, it can be skipped. Only some of the questions regarding administrative information are mandatory in the survey. If the provider in question is operating several environments, it is advisable to answer the survey for all of them separately.

The survey closes at midnight CET on Friday, 4th July 2025. The deadline may be extended if needed.

*) <https://hdruk.github.io/TRE-Survey/>

***) <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18PwtsEjfJC-LOsySsp6bjMh4yKJFdpxy/view?usp=sharing>

Target audience

This survey is directed at all who identify themselves as trusted research environment providers or who are interested in being included in the EOSC ENTRUST TRE inventory. It is up to the providers to choose the most suitable individual experts to draft and submit the survey responses. We do not collect personal identifiers from the individuals submitting responses for this survey.

Premise/purpose of survey

One of the EOSC-ENTRUST project's tasks is to create an inventory of TREs. This survey serves the purpose of the inventory, as well as capability mapping and gap analysis. The aim is also to collect initial sets of high-level requirements and best practices on TREs from providers. In addition, the outcomes will give input for the TRE blueprint to be developed by the EOSC-ENTRUST project. The inventory will be updated at least once more during the project, which will allow adding new information categories and widening the scope of included providers and environments. Based on the survey, a public TRE inventory will be published, so please take this into consideration when providing your answers.

Use of answers

Answers will be used for the second iteration of the TRE inventory, one of EOSC-ENTRUST project milestones. In this second phase, the inventory will be published on the project website and the

project Zenodo repository (by the end of August 2025). The data will be managed and stored during the project and after the project according to the EOSC-ENTRUST project data management plan, consortium agreement, and other relevant project guidelines.

What do we mean by TRE in the context of this survey?

For the purpose of this survey, a trusted research environment (TRE) is any digital solution, or an interoperable collection of solutions, specifically intended for handling sensitive research data. There are other terms also in use for environments for handling sensitive data, such as secure processing environment (SPE) and data safe haven, etc. This survey is NOT intended only for those solutions that self-identify as TREs. The aim is to collect information from all and any environments for handling sensitive data by service providers.

About EOSC-ENTRUST

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project brings together providers of operational TREs from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language. This blueprint for interoperability is anchored in the EOSC Interoperability Framework spanning the four dimensions of legal, organisational, technical and semantic interoperability. EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects covering genomics, clinical trials, social science and public private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows.

Contact person for the survey

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Organisational details

Information about the organisation hosting the environment

1. Name of the environment *
2. Name of host organisation *
3. [Organisation ROR](#) *
4. Organisation two-letter [country code](#) *

Functional Capabilities

Description of the type of the environment and its main use cases

5. Please provide a service self-description

- Tick all that apply.
- Trusted Research Environment (TRE)
- Safe Processing Environment (SPE)
- Data Safe Haven
- HPC
- Remote access system
- Other:

6. What is the GDPR role of the organisation?

Mark only one oval.

- Data controller
- Data processor
- Both

7. What TRE service zones are present?

Tick all that apply.

- TRE/RAZ
- TRE/DMZ
- TRE/DQZ

8. Is the environment available only for processing sensitive data use cases?

Mark only one oval.

- Dedicated to sensitive data
- Multi-purpose

9. Public description of environment (URL)

10. Is the service available only for public benefit purposes?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- N/A

Access mechanisms

Information about how access to the environment is enabled

11. Is there a self-service user login?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

12. Is there a two-factor authentication?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

13. Is there single sign-on?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

International Accessibility & Accepted Data Types

Referring to the accessibility of the environment, e.g. can it be accessed from other EU countries, and information on which technical data types are accepted for import and export.

14. From which countries can the environment be accessed?

Mark only one oval.

- Only national access possible
- Access from other EU countries
- Access from other EEA countries
- Non-EU access possible
- Other:

15. From what region can the PI be registered?

Mark only one oval.

- Only national registration possible
- Registration from other EU countries

- Registration from other EEA countries
- Non-EU registration possible
- Other:

16. From what region can non-PI project members be registered?

Mark only one oval.

- Only national registration possible
- Registration from other EU countries
- Registration from other EEA countries
- Non-EU registration possible

17. Is there a premise/private cloud, public cloud, or hybrid?

Mark only one oval.

- Private
- Public
- Hybrid
- N/A

18. What are the supported technical data types inside the environment?

Tick all that apply.

- Plain text files
- Document files
- Spreadsheet files
- Source code
- Images
- DICOM files
- Binary data in proprietary format
- Unrestricted data types
- Other:

19. What are the supported technical data types for export?

Tick all that apply.

- Plain text files
- Document files
- Spreadsheet files
- Images
- DICOM files
- Source code
- Binary data in proprietary format
- Unrestricted
- Other:

Auditing and Security Measures

Information on security measures taken to ensure the security of the environment

20. Does the service have an ISO27001 certification?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- In progress

21. Are there other security audits and certificates?

Tick all that apply.

- National
- Regional
- Organisational
- Other:

22. Are project areas fully isolated from each other?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

23. What are the security measures against unauthorised access?

Tick all that apply.

- Multi Factor Authentication
- Federated user accounts
- Individual identification
- Other:

24. What are the security measures for mitigating data loss?

Tick all that apply.

- Data backup
- Snapshots
- User guidelines
- Cybersecurity measures
- Other:

25. What are the security measures for mitigating misuse by users?

Tick all that apply.

- Authorised access
- Export encryptions
- Sanctions
- Certifications
- User restrictions
- User training
- Other:

Computing and Analysis Services

Computing and analysis services available for the user, such as information on the operating system, analysis software and tools available

26. What is the standard base operating system?

Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Linux
- Rocky
- Ubuntu
- Redhat Enterprise
- Unix
- CentOS Stream
- Other:

27. What operating systems are available to users?

Mark only one oval.

- Windows
- Linux
- macOS
- ChromeOS
- Other:

28. Is there access to HPC in/through the environment?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

29. What tooling is provided?

- Mark only one oval.
- Tensor Flow
- Pytorch
- Keras
- Scikit
- RStudio
- Jupyter notebooks
- Custom-made analysis software
- Other:

30. Is there support for AI/machine learning?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

User Rights

What rights and restrictions does the user have in the environment, e.g. can own packages be installed?

31. Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- N/A

32. What is the user import source?

Tick all that apply.

- Clipboard
- Unregulated network access
- Network access regulated by TRE
- Network access regulated by external entity
- Other:

33. What is the user import size?

Mark only one oval.

- Any
- Limited

34. What is the user import type?

Tick all that apply.

- Any
- Text only
- Source code
- Containers
- Data
- Other:

35. What is the user import connection?

Mark only one oval.

- Unregulated
- Encrypted
- Limited to stated internal addresses
- Limited to any stated address
- Other:

36. What conditions are there on users importing code/software/libraries?

Mark only one oval.

- No restrictions
- Imports are checked - automated
- Imports are checked - manual
- Sampling - automated (some imports checked)
- Sampling - manual (some imports checked)
- No imports by users

37. What measures are there against malicious code execution?

Tick all that apply.

- Antivirus checks for all imports
- Regular monitoring
- Restrictions on route access
- Other:

Data Discovery, Federated Analysis and Architecture

Referring to the availability of a public discovery service for datasets, if support for federated analysis is provided, and a description of the architecture the environment is based on

38. Is there a public discovery service for datasets available in this TRE?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

39. Please provide a link to the public discovery service

40. Does the service support federated queries? Please provide details.

41. Does the service support federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users? Please provide details.

42. Does the environment follow a specific reference architecture?

Mark only one oval.

- SATRE
- National reference architecture
- Institutional reference architecture
- EOSC ENTRUST blueprint
- Other: